

Highlights

A Time Series Classification Framework Based on Autoregressive Modeling

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- ARTSC introduces a domain-independent time series classification approach based on autoregressive modeling.
- The method is designed for versatility and applicability across diverse datasets.
- Competitive results on UCR & UEA benchmark datasets highlight ARTSC's robustness.

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Aykut Tayyip Altay^a, Mustafa Gökçe Baydoğan^a

^a*Boğaziçi University, Industrial Engineering, Bebek, Istanbul, 34342, Turkey*

Abstract

Time series data arise in a variety of real-world applications, such as stock market analysis, weather forecasting, speech recognition, and health-care monitoring, where capturing temporal dependencies is critical. Although many task-oriented studies based on autoregressive (AR) modeling exist in the literature, to the best of our knowledge, Autoregressive Time Series Classification (ARTSC) is the first domain-independent method for time series classification. The rationale behind ARTSC is the assumption that each time series can be modeled as an autoregressive (AR) process, and that features extracted from this process can be effectively utilized for classification tasks. ARTSC distinguishes itself from other commonly used time series classification methods by combining simplicity with ease of applicability. ARTSC's performance was evaluated by comparing its error rates with those of widely used methods on benchmark datasets from the UCR & UEA time series database. The results show that ARTSC achieved comparable or better performance.

Keywords: Time Series Classification, Autoregressive Modeling, Machine

1. Introduction

Time series data are widely used in real-world applications such as medicine, agriculture, and finance, where accurately capturing temporal dependencies is essential. While many existing methods are designed for specific application areas, domain-independent approaches remain limited. Autoregressive (AR) modeling, which effectively represents time series processes, forms the basis of the proposed Autoregressive Time Series Classification (ARTSC) method. ARTSC uses features derived from AR models to perform accurate and efficient classification, offering simplicity and broad applicability compared to commonly used methods.

Time series classification methods are broadly divided into two categories: Instance-based (IB) and feature-based (FB) methods. In IB methods, the class of a test instance is determined by evaluating the similarity between the test instance and the training instances, typically using similarity measures such as Euclidean Distance (ED) and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [1]. In FB methods, time series are transformed into a feature space by extracting structural patterns. These features may include coefficients derived from representations generated by techniques such as the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) [2] or statistical characteristics such as skewness or kurtosis [3].

A subtype of feature-based methods that has recently gained popularity is model-based (MB) classification methods, which rely on statistical mod-

eling of time series to capture the underlying structure of time series. Examples of such models include Autoregressive (AR), Moving Average (MA), Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA), Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). AR models estimate current values based on recent past observations, capturing dependencies where recent values exert significant influence, while MA models focus on short-term dependencies by modeling current values as a function of past random errors. ARMA combines AR and MA components to handle stationary series, while ARIMA extends ARMA with differencing, making it well-suited for non-stationary series with trends or seasonality commonly observed in real-world data. HMMs, on the other hand, are probabilistic models that describe sequences of observations as generated by a series of hidden states, making them particularly effective for capturing temporal dynamics in complex time series. For example, Jastrzebska et al. [4] proposed a feature-based time series classification method that utilizes the parameters of the ARIMA model as features. To further enhance classification, the approach includes up to 30% of randomly selected time series data points as additional features. These features are then used to train general-purpose classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF) [5] and Support Vector Machines (SVM) [6], for classification tasks. The authors demonstrated the effectiveness of their method on benchmark datasets, showing that it performs competitively against both plain classifiers and other feature-based approaches.

On the other hand, Kotsifakos and Papapetrou [7] propose a model-

based (MB) method called MTSC, which integrates Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) with a filter-and-refine framework for effective and efficient time series classification. In MTSC, each class of time series is represented by an HMM trained on class-specific data, capturing the underlying probabilistic structure of the sequences. During classification, the framework begins by identifying the top K HMMs most likely to have generated the query time series, using the Forward algorithm [8] to calculate likelihoods. In the refine step, a distance measure is applied to compare the query with all training time series belonging to the top K models. The query is then assigned to the class of the nearest neighbor within these time series. This approach balances classification accuracy and computational efficiency by reducing the search space in the refine step.

The foundation of ARTSC lies in the assumption that an observed time series can be modeled as an autoregressive (AR) process, and that features extracted from this process can serve as the basis for a classification method. ARTSC comprises four main steps. First, the optimal values for the autoregressive parameters, lag (p) and differencing (d), are determined using a grid search technique. To ensure stationarity, the Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) test [9] is applied, and only stationary configurations are considered for the grid search. Next, features are extracted from the time series data. The *total fitting error* for all instances is calculated, and the coefficients of the AR model are computed. Additionally, the first p raw data values are retained to address the potential loss of valuable information

in the initial p values of the time series. Once the feature set is prepared, a Random Forest (RF) classifier is trained using these features. The classifier is then evaluated on the test dataset, allowing for performance assessment.

The primary contribution of this research is the introduction of ARTSC as a domain-independent time series classification method based on AR modeling. Although some task-oriented studies have utilized AR modeling, to the best of our knowledge, no previous study has proposed a general framework for time series classification based on this approach. In the machine learning community, classification algorithms are commonly evaluated based on two criteria: classification accuracy on benchmark datasets and algorithmic complexity [10]. While there are highly accurate algorithms, such as COTE [11], they tend to be complex and computationally intensive. Conversely, some simple algorithms can achieve high accuracy on many datasets. As Holte [10] highlights, learning systems that rely on simple rules can provide effective alternatives to those requiring more complex rules—a principle that has gained considerable attention over the years. ARTSC exemplifies this approach as a simple yet effective method for time series classification. Extensive experiments were conducted to assess the effectiveness of ARTSC, and the results indicate that despite its simplicity, ARTSC achieves competitive accuracy levels compared to widely used methods in time series classification. Notably, ARTSC yields the highest accuracy for datasets in the *Device*, and *Sensor* categories.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews re-

lated works. Section 3 outlines the theoretical background. Section 4 details the proposed method and its theoretical foundations. Section 5 presents the experimental results across various datasets. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper with a discussion and future research directions.

2. Related Work

Autoregressive (AR) models have been widely used in classification tasks, with many studies focusing on applications within specific branches of medicine. For instance, Ge et al. [12] introduce a pioneering study that applied AR modeling to classify cardiac arrhythmias in critically ill patients, providing a robust framework for automated arrhythmia detection. Their method optimized model order selection using the correlation coefficient (ρ) and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) to ensure accurate signal representation. They subsequently employed a stage-wise generalized linear model (GLM) classifier, using AR model coefficients to distinguish normal ECG signals from various arrhythmias. This work demonstrated the effectiveness of AR-based methods for reliable diagnostics in clinical settings

Another branch of health research employing AR models focuses on brain activity analysis, as seen in the work by Zhang et al. [13], which explores EEG signal classification using autoregressive modeling combined with wavelet packet decomposition (WPD). The authors propose two feature extraction strategies for EEG classification: one combining AR coefficients with approximate entropy (ApEn), and another using WPD to decompose EEG signals

into sub-bands, followed by AR coefficient calculation. Both feature sets are classified using a support vector machine (SVM), with experimental results showing that the WPD-AR combination provides superior classification accuracy, especially when the AR model order is greater than five. This approach shows that combining time-frequency analysis with AR modeling works well for classifying EEG-based brain activity.

Recently, Attia et al. [14], introduced an AR-based automated framework for detecting and classifying epileptic seizures in EEG signals. Their approach integrates an AR model with the firefly optimization algorithm (FA) and support vector machines (SVM) to aid neurophysiologists by automating seizure analysis and improving detection reliability. Feature extraction begins with an AR model generating features from EEG data, followed by FA, guided by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), to determine the optimal model order, thereby reducing noise and enhancing classification accuracy. The FA further refines this process by selecting the most representative model parameters, after which SVM effectively classifies the extracted features due to its established efficacy in EEG data classification.

In contrast to studies focused on cardiology and neurology, Bringmann et al. [15] introduced a time-varying autoregressive (TV-AR) model [16] for psychological time series, where non-stationary processes arise from changing dynamics over time. Unlike traditional AR models, which assume constant parameters, the TV-AR model allows these parameters to vary, making it suitable for both stationary and non-stationary data. The authors employed

a generalized additive model (GAM) framework to let AR parameters evolve flexibly over time, capturing gradual shifts without needing predefined change patterns. Through simulations and empirical examples, they demonstrated that the TV-AR model effectively models dynamic psychological states, offering a valuable tool for research into changing psychological processes.

Since the assumptions of linearity and stationarity of the aforementioned models are not always suitable for real world problems, many alternative methods based on nonlinear behavior of time series have been proposed recently. For example, Ouyang and Yin [17] introduced a combined neural model for tackling the problems of nonlinearity and nonstationarity in time series data about foreign exchange (FX) rates. The proposed model, neural gas mixture of autoregressive models (NGMAR), is able to effectively model FX rates time series by taking the advantage of dynamic neighborhood rankings of neural gas and a similarity measure of the sum of autocorrelation coefficients [17].

Unlike the aforementioned methods, which are designed for specific tasks in fields like cardiology, neurology, and finance, ARTSC provides a *domain-independent* framework for time series classification. While many existing approaches combine AR modeling with complex measures, optimization techniques, or non-stationary adaptations, ARTSC keeps computations practical even for larger datasets by dynamically adjusting the lag order (p) and differencing parameter (d) based on dataset complexity. Besides, ARTSC combines AR modeling with a Random Forest classifier, enhancing its robustness

and flexibility.

3. Theoretical Background

In this part of the paper, we will introduce the theoretical basis of the research: Autoregressive modeling, fitting an autoregressive model, random forests, and some widely used time series classification methods.

3.1. Autoregressive Modeling

An autoregressive (AR) model of order p for a stationary time series $\{Y_t, t \in Z\}$ is defined as:

$$y_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i y_{t-i} + e_t, \quad (1)$$

where y_t is the value at time t , c is a constant, θ_i are the AR coefficients, and e_t is Gaussian white noise with zero mean and constant variance. In AR models, the value at time t is modeled as a linear combination of the past p values, making them interpretable and effective for capturing temporal dependencies.

Stationarity and Differencing

A time series is stationary if its statistical properties, such as mean and variance, remain constant over time. To handle nonstationary series, ARTSC

applies differencing, defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{First difference: } y'_t &= y_t - y_{t-1}, \\ \text{Second difference: } y''_t &= y'_t - y'_{t-1}, \\ &\vdots \\ n^{\text{th}} \text{ difference: } y_t^{(n)} &= y_t^{(n-1)} - y_{t-1}^{(n-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

3.2. Fitting an Autoregressive Model

Fitting an autoregressive (AR) model is a foundational technique in time series analysis. In an AR model, the current value of the series is expressed as a linear combination of its past values. The general form of an AR model is:

$$y_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i y_{t-i} + e_t,$$

where y_t represents the value at time t , θ_i are the AR coefficients, and e_t is the noise term.

Estimating AR Coefficients

Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) is a common method for estimating AR coefficients. This statistical technique determines parameters by maximizing the likelihood of observing the given time series data under the AR model.

Fitted Values and Total Fitting Error

The fitted values for a time series $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N\}$ are calculated as:

$$\hat{y}_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i y_{t-i},$$

for $t > p$. For the first p values (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p) , fitted values cannot be computed due to insufficient lagged terms and are set equal to the original values:

$$\hat{y}_t = y_t, \quad \text{for } t \leq p.$$

The difference between the observed and fitted values gives the error term e_t :

$$e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t.$$

The Total Fitting Error (TFE) is defined as the sum of squared errors:

$$TFE = \sum_{t=p+1}^N e_t^2.$$

Practical Considerations

Selecting the optimal lag order (p) is crucial in fitting AR models, as it determines how much past information is used for prediction. In ARTSC, this parameter is dynamically tuned based on dataset complexity, balancing computational efficiency with model accuracy. Stationarity is another key requirement for AR models, which ARTSC addresses by applying the KPSS test and dynamically adjusting the differencing parameter (d) to handle non-stationarity. This adaptability allows ARTSC to effectively accommodate

both stationary and non-stationary time series.

In addition to stationarity, estimating AR coefficients is critical for scalability, particularly when dealing with large datasets or high lag orders. While Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) provides precise parameter estimates, it can be computationally intensive. To address this, ARTSC primarily employs MLE but also supports Conditional Sum of Squares with Maximum Likelihood (CSS-ML) as a faster alternative for scenarios where rapid results are required [18]. Additionally, ARTSC dynamically limits p and d to values appropriate for the dataset’s complexity, reducing computational costs while maintaining reliable accuracy.

3.3. Random Forests

Random Forest (RF) plays a critical role in ARTSC by serving as the classification model that integrates AR-derived features. Its ensemble structure, built from multiple decision trees, enhances robustness to noise and irrelevant features, providing reliable classification across diverse datasets. RF’s ability to handle high-dimensional data and model non-linear decision boundaries complements the simplicity of AR-based features in ARTSC.

In ARTSC, adequate values for RF hyperparameters, such as the number of trees (n_{tree}) and the minimum size of terminal nodes ($nodesize$), are set based on the category of the dataset, determined by its Complexity Score, as defined in the next section, Proposed Method. This approach maintains a balance between computational efficiency and classification performance, making ARTSC an effective method for time series classification.

3.4. *Some Widely Used Time Series Classification Methods*

In this section of the paper, we introduce some commonly used time series classification methods briefly, which will be used to evaluate the success of the proposed method.

1. C4.5: One of the most widely used decision tree algorithms, introduced by Quinlan [19].
2. MLP (Multilayer Perceptron): A feedforward artificial neural network method that uses backpropagation for training.
3. 1NN-Euclid: 1-nearest neighbor method that uses Euclidean distance as the measure of distance.
4. 1NN-DTW: 1-nearest neighbor method that uses DTW (Dynamic Time Warping) as the measure of distance.
5. 1NN-LCSS: 1-nearest neighbor method that uses LCSS (Least Common Subsequence as the measure of distance
6. SVM: Stands for support vector machines that performs linear classification, which is a highly successful learning algorithm introduced by Cortes and Vapnik [6].
7. FS: Stands for fast shapelets, FS is a recently developed time series classification method based on the notion of shapelet, i.e. a time series snippet that might represent time series characteristics [20].

4. Proposed Method

4.1. Introduction to the Method

Since the proposed method uses features extracted from the autoregressive modeling of time series, it is called *Autoregressive Time Series Classification* (ARTSC). The ARTSC framework is outlined in the following four primary steps and is also illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Main Steps of ARTSC

- 1. Determine the optimal lag (p) and differencing (d):** The process begins by determining the optimal values for the lag parameter (p) and differencing parameter (d) through grid search combined with cross-validation. The maximum values for these parameters, p_{max} and d_{max} ,

are dynamically adjusted based on the complexity score of the training dataset (D_{train}), which is defined in Step 4.

2. **Compute total fitting errors for all instances:** For each combination of p and d that satisfies the stationarity condition determined by the KPSS test, the total fitting error (TFE) is computed for all instances.
3. **Compute the values of features:** Using the optimal p and d values, ARTSC extracts three types of features: the first p raw data points, the AR coefficients, and the total fitting error (TFE). These features are used to form the feature dataset, which encapsulates temporal dependencies, raw data information, and predictive performance.
4. **Complete the classification by using a RF classifier:** The extracted features are used to train a Random Forest (RF) classifier. The final model is evaluated on the test dataset (D_{test}), and the results, including accuracy, are reported. ARTSC implements a dynamic tuning strategy for RF hyperparameters to adapt to varying dataset complexities. A heuristic **Complexity Score** is computed using the formula:

$$\text{Complexity Score} = \frac{P \cdot C}{\log(M + 1)},$$

where P is the number of predictors, M is the number of training instances, and C is the number of classes. This score reflects the dimensionality of the feature space (P), the classification task difficulty (C), and the dataset size (M), with larger datasets reducing overall

complexity. Based on this score, datasets are classified into three categories: *simple*, *moderate*, and *complex*. ARTSC uses these categories to set RF parameters, such as the number of trees (*ntree*) and the minimum size of terminal nodes (*nodesize*), balancing computational efficiency with classification performance.

To better understand the output of the feature extraction process, consider a hypothetical two-class dataset where the lag value (p) is set to 3. The extracted features include the three autoregressive (AR) coefficients (Coef1, Coef2, Coef3), the first three values of each time series (Val1, Val2, Val3), the total fitting error (Total Fit Error), and the class label (Class). These features collectively form the feature frame used for classification. An example of such a feature frame is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Example Features Data Frame for a Two-Class Dataset

Coef1	Coef2	Coef3	Val1	Val2	Val3	Total Fit Error	Class
0.45123	0.35289	0.11234	1.52345	1.41789	1.29456	0.23489	1
0.38912	0.28345	0.09123	2.78123	2.65478	2.51234	0.19876	1
0.28745	0.20123	0.07456	0.93456	0.81234	0.71234	0.27534	2
0.50123	0.41123	0.11245	1.82345	1.70123	1.51234	0.31234	2

Experiments across multiple datasets, as visualized in Figure 2, revealed a consistent pattern among the most important features: at least one autoregressive (AR) coefficient (e.g., $c7$, $c8$), one raw data point (e.g., $t4$, $t11$), and the total fitting error (TFE, labeled as *error_value*) frequently rank highly. This recurring observation validates the inclusion of these three feature types in ARTSC, as they collectively capture temporal dependencies, retain critical

raw information, and reflect model predictive performance.

Figure 2: Top-ranked features for the ECG200 dataset, highlighting their importance.

4.2. General Algorithm and Computational Complexity of ALTS

The algorithm for the developed method is introduced in Algorithm 1. The computational complexity of ARTSC is determined by the main steps of the algorithm, including preprocessing, KPSS stationarity testing, grid search for optimal parameters, classifier training, and feature importance computation. Among these, the grid search dominates the complexity due to the exhaustive evaluation of parameter combinations using cross-validation.

For a dataset with M time series instances, each of length N , and maximum lag and differencing values of p_{\max} and d_{\max} , respectively, the total complexity of ARTSC can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{O}(d_{\max}p_{\max}cv_{\text{folds}}MNp),$$

where cv_{folds} is the number of CV folds and p is the actual lag value.

Algorithm 1 General Algorithm of ARTSC

Require: $D \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$: Time Series Dataset

M : Number of Instances, N : Length of each Instance

$D_{\text{train}}, D_{\text{test}}$: Predefined Training and Test Datasets

p_{max} : Maximum Lag Value, d_{max} : Maximum Differencing Value

$P_{\text{threshold}}$: P-value Threshold for KPSS Stationarity Test

method: Classification Method (e.g., Random Forest (RF))

Ensure: Best Parameters p^*, d^* , Training/Test Accuracy

- 1: Compute the *complexity score* of D_{train}
 - 2: Dynamically set p_{max} and d_{max} based on the *complexity score*
 - 3: **for** $d = 0$ **to** d_{max} **do**
 - 4: Perform KPSS Test on D_{train} with differencing order d
 - 5: **if** KPSS Test P-value $> P_{\text{threshold}}$ (indicates non-stationarity) **then**
 - 6: **continue**
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: **for** $p = 2$ **to** p_{max} **do**
 - 9: Generate AR-based features for D_{train} using lag p
 - 10: Remove constant features
 - 11: Perform cross-validation using dynamically adjusted RF parameters
 - 12: **if** Cross-validation accuracy improves **then**
 - 13: $p^* \leftarrow p, d^* \leftarrow d$
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: Train the final model with p^* and d^* on D_{train} and evaluate on D_{test}
 - 19: Save results: p^*, d^* , Training/Test Accuracy
 - 20: **return** p^*, d^* , Training Accuracy, Test Accuracy
-

5. Experiments and Results

The algorithm of ARTSC is implemented in the R programming language, and extensive experiments are conducted to evaluate its performance using datasets from the UCR&UEA time series classification archive [21], a widely recognized benchmark in the field. In the initial phase of experimentation, the best parameter settings for lag (p) and differencing (d) values are determined through cross-validation, guided by ARTSC’s complexity-aware parameter tuning strategy. The optimal values of p and d are selected to maximize classification accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency. The coefficients of the autoregressive model are computed using the `arima` function from R’s `stats` package [22], with the MLE method employed for precise parameter estimation.

The results achieved by ARTSC are compared with those of several widely-used time series classification methods, including C4.5, MLP, 1NN-Euclidean, 1NN-DTW, 1NN-LCSS, SVMML, and FS. These comparisons, presented in Table 3 and Table 4, highlight ARTSC’s competitive performance across various datasets. A legend for interpreting the symbols and abbreviations in the tables is provided in Table 2.

The best parameter settings, i.e., the optimal lag (p) and differencing (d) values identified for each dataset, are publicly available on the ARTSC GitHub repository [23]. Baseline scores for the comparison methods listed in the tables are accessible at [24].

Table 2: Legend for the Dataset Categories and Number of Datasets

Type	Symbol	Number of Datasets
Device	¥	6
ECG	□	7
Image	△	27
Motion	⊗	13
Sensor	●	15
Simulated	◇	5
Spectro	§	7

Table 3: ARTSC: Comparison of Accuracy Levels - Part 1

Dataset	C45	MLP	1NN-Euclid	1NN-DTW	1NN-LCSS	SVML	FS	ARTSC
Adiac △	0.542	0.737	0.611	0.609	0.251	0.442	0.593	0.66
ArrowHead △	0.606	0.709	0.800	0.800	0.789	0.731	0.594	0.669
Beef §	0.533	0.600	0.667	0.667	0.767	0.900	0.567	0.767
BeetleFly △	0.900	0.800	0.750	0.650	0.800	0.800	0.700	0.850
BirdChicken △	0.800	0.600	0.550	0.700	0.800	0.650	0.750	0.900
CBF ◇	0.673	0.894	0.852	0.994	0.990	0.878	0.940	0.950
ChlorineConcentration ◇	0.688	0.861	0.650	0.650	0.720	0.584	0.546	0.677
CinCECGtorso □	0.590	0.462	0.897	0.930	0.946	0.469	0.859	0.829
Coffee §	0.929	0.964	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.929	0.964
Computers ¥	0.568	0.496	0.576	0.624	0.644	0.492	0.500	0.616
CricketX ⊗	0.274	0.505	0.577	0.754	0.731	0.390	0.485	0.574
CricketY ⊗	0.328	0.526	0.567	0.744	0.787	0.459	0.531	0.521
CricketZ ⊗	0.321	0.544	0.587	0.754	0.741	0.379	0.464	0.533
DiatomSizeReduction △	0.716	0.964	0.935	0.935	0.941	0.954	0.866	0.876
DistalPhalanxOutlineCorrect △	0.757	0.822	0.717	0.725	0.743	0.663	0.750	0.792
DistalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup △	0.691	0.806	0.626	0.626	0.734	0.712	0.655	0.742
DistalPhalanxTW △	0.626	0.626	0.633	0.633	0.633	0.705	0.626	0.676
Earthquakes ●	0.698	0.698	0.712	0.727	0.727	0.640	0.705	0.770
ECG200 □	0.800	0.790	0.880	0.880	0.890	0.810	0.810	0.900
ECG5000 □	0.899	0.933	0.925	0.925	0.930	0.938	0.923	0.936
ECGFiveDays □	0.721	0.916	0.797	0.797	0.794	0.976	0.998	0.933
ElectricDevices ¥	0.559	0.641	0.552	0.602	0.626	0.498	0.579	0.655
FaceAll △	0.549	0.863	0.714	0.808	0.801	0.720	0.626	0.705
FacesUCR △	0.478	0.747	0.769	0.908	0.955	0.758	0.706	0.583
FiftyWords △	0.418	0.651	0.631	0.765	0.798	0.646	0.481	0.493
Fish △	0.566	0.846	0.783	0.834	0.874	0.851	0.783	0.617
FordA ●	0.562	0.745	0.665	0.665	0.698	0.496	0.787	0.972
FordB ●	0.526	0.665	0.606	0.599	0.648	0.527	0.728	0.928
GunPoint ⊗	0.773	0.927	0.913	0.913	0.973	0.800	0.947	0.933
Ham §	0.533	0.838	0.600	0.600	0.610	0.600	0.648	0.618
HandOutlines △	0.881	0.884	0.862	0.878	0.849	0.892	0.811	0.705
Haptics ⊗	0.351	0.468	0.370	0.416	0.390	0.406	0.393	0.451

Table 4: ARTSC: Comparison of Accuracy Levels - Part 2

Dataset	C45	MLP	1NN-Euclid	1NN-DTW	1NN-LCSS	SVML	FS	ARTSC
Herring \triangle	0.578	0.641	0.516	0.531	0.562	0.609	0.531	0.719
InlineSkate \square	0.269	0.340	0.342	0.387	0.427	0.309	0.189	0.591
InsectWingbeatSound \bullet	0.507	0.591	0.562	0.574	0.556	0.643	0.489	0.537
ItalyPowerDemand \bullet	0.947	0.946	0.955	0.955	0.957	0.972	0.917	0.960
LargeKitchenAppliances \yen	0.485	0.480	0.493	0.795	0.584	0.427	0.560	0.672
Lightning2 \bullet	0.623	0.721	0.754	0.869	0.770	0.721	0.705	0.692
Lightning7 \bullet	0.548	0.644	0.575	0.712	0.575	0.712	0.644	0.575
Mallat \diamond	0.751	0.895	0.914	0.914	0.911	0.867	0.976	0.829
Meat \S	0.867	1.000	0.933	0.933	0.533	0.967	0.833	0.900
MedicalImages \triangle	0.625	0.705	0.684	0.747	0.707	0.616	0.624	0.722
MiddlePhalanxOutlineCorrect \triangle	0.698	0.808	0.766	0.766	0.749	0.636	0.729	0.780
MiddlePhalanxOutlineAgeGroup \triangle	0.552	0.558	0.519	0.519	0.610	0.617	0.545	0.623
MiddlePhalanxTW \triangle	0.494	0.571	0.513	0.506	0.578	0.578	0.532	0.598
MoteStrain \bullet	0.787	0.846	0.879	0.866	0.882	0.867	0.777	0.875
NonInvasiveFatalECGThorax1 \square	0.719	0.926	0.829	0.829	0.812	0.923	0.710	0.825
NonInvasiveFatalECGThorax2 \square	0.785	0.945	0.880	0.870	0.883	0.942	0.754	0.854
OliveOil \S	0.833	0.900	0.867	0.867	0.400	0.867	0.733	0.767
OSULeaf \triangle	0.343	0.459	0.521	0.599	0.789	0.442	0.678	0.777
PhalangesOutlinesCorrect \triangle	0.734	0.837	0.761	0.761	0.742	0.647	0.744	0.783
Phoneme \bullet	0.065	0.097	0.109	0.227	0.256	0.094	0.174	0.229
Plane \bullet	0.962	0.962	0.962	1.000	1.000	0.981	1.000	1.000
ProximalPhalanxOutlineCorrect \triangle	0.797	0.866	0.808	0.790	0.756	0.825	0.804	0.876
ProximalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup \triangle	0.834	0.800	0.785	0.785	0.854	0.854	0.780	0.849
ProximalPhalanxTW \triangle	0.737	0.790	0.707	0.761	0.805	0.824	0.702	0.781
RefrigerationDevices \yen	0.464	0.368	0.395	0.440	0.491	0.352	0.333	0.523
ScreenType \yen	0.373	0.387	0.360	0.411	0.437	0.381	0.413	0.512
ShapeletSim \diamond	0.489	0.472	0.539	0.694	0.822	0.489	1.000	0.961
ShapesAll \triangle	0.472	0.650	0.752	0.802	0.845	0.713	0.580	0.583
SmallKitchenAppliances \yen	0.573	0.333	0.344	0.672	0.472	0.461	0.333	0.701
SonyAIBORobotSurface1 \bullet	0.656	0.902	0.696	0.696	0.735	0.704	0.686	1.000
SonyAIBORobotSurface2 \bullet	0.686	0.841	0.859	0.859	0.811	0.818	0.790	0.975

5.1. Statistical Analysis of Results

5.1.1. ARTSC compared to some widely-used methods

The accuracy levels of ARTSC and other methods were evaluated using the *Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed-rank test* [25], a robust non-parametric test that identifies significant pairwise differences in accuracy. This test was chosen as an alternative to the paired t-test, as it does not assume normality in the data. The *p-values* and *win/loss* ratios for ARTSC compared to other methods are presented in Table 5. ARTSC achieves statistically significant improvements over methods such as C45, 1NN Euclid, SVMML, and FS, as indicated by the low p-values and favorable win/loss ratios. For MLP, 1NN DTW, and 1NN LCSS, while no significant differences are observed, ARTSC maintains a competitive performance, as reflected in the balanced win/loss ratios.

Table 5: ARTSC P-Values and Win/Loss Ratios

Statistics Used	C45	MLP	1NN Euclid	1NN DTW	1NN LCSS	SVMML	FS
P-Value	0.000	0.149	0.001	0.589	0.483	0.001	0.000
Win/Loss Ratio	72/8	45/34	50/29	44/35	43/34	50/30	57/21

To complement the pairwise analysis provided by the Wilcoxon test, we employed the Friedman Test [26] to assess differences across all classifiers simultaneously. The test ranks classifiers on each dataset, providing a robust comparison without relying on raw accuracy values. The Friedman Test rejected the null hypothesis ($p = 0.000$), confirming significant differences in performance among the classifiers. To further investigate these differences, the Nemenyi post-hoc test [27] was applied. A critical difference (CD) of

1.174 at a significance level of 0.05 was calculated to identify statistically significant pairwise differences.

The results of the Friedman and Nemenyi [28] tests are visualized in Figure 3. ARTSC achieved a mean rank (MR) of 3.438, demonstrating strong overall performance, closely following 1NN-LCSS (MR=3.319). In contrast, C45 exhibited the weakest performance with the highest mean rank of 6.550, followed by FS (MR=5.244), SVML (MR=4.869), and 1NN-Euclid (MR=4.787). MLP (MR=4.062) and 1NN-DTW (MR=3.731) performed better but ranked below ARTSC. Therefore we conclude that there are no significant differences within the following groups: FS, SVML, and 1NN-Euclid; SVML, 1NN-Euclid, MLP, and 1NN-DTW; MLP, 1NN-DTW, ARTSC, and 1NN-LCSS. All other differences are significant.

Figure 3: Critical Distance Diagram for ARTSC

5.1.2. *ARTSC compared to two model-based methods*

To the best of our knowledge, **ARTSC** is the first domain-independent time series classification method based on autoregressive (AR) modeling. Given its distinct approach, there are no directly comparable methods in the literature. However, to contextualize its performance relative to existing model-based time series classification methods, we compare ARTSC with two notable approaches: an ARIMA-based method [4] and a Hidden Markov Model (HMM)-based method referred to as **MTSC** [7].

The ARIMA-based method reports results on 30 datasets from the UCR&UEA archive, while MTSC uses 33 datasets. ARTSC evaluates its performance on a broader set of 80 datasets. For a fair comparison, we restrict our analysis to the 7 datasets that are common among ARTSC, ARIMA, and MTSC. Due to the limited number of shared datasets, we do not perform statistical significance tests, as the small sample size may not provide reliable conclusions. Instead, we report the accuracy results for these datasets.

The accuracy levels achieved by ARTSC, ARIMA, and MTSC on the common datasets are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Comparison of the Accuracy Levels of the Three Methods

Dataset	ARTSC	ARIMA	MTSC
Beef	0.767	0.800	0.533
ChlorineConcentration	0.677	0.781	0.596
CricketY	0.521	0.610	0.800
DiatomSizeReduction	0.876	0.931	0.954
InlineSkate	0.591	0.482	0.426
Lightning7	0.575	0.781	0.781
Trace	1.000	0.950	1.000

5.2. Rank Analysis by Type

The best-performing algorithms, categorized by problem type as described in [29], are presented in Table 7. The table follows a simple scoring rationale: if a method achieves the best accuracy among the compared methods for a given dataset, it is awarded 1 point. If multiple methods share the highest accuracy, the point is divided equally among them. For instance, as shown in Table 3, there are four methods that achieve the best accuracy for the *Coffee* dataset, with each method receiving 0.25 points. Based on the total points in the Table 7, ARTSC emerges as the best-performing method overall, achieving the highest total score of 21.75. However, its performance is dataset-dependent, as it dominates in categories like Device and Sensor but contributes no points in others such as Simulated and Spectro.

The values in Table 7 are converted to percentages and introduced in this form in Table 8 for easy interpretation of results. For example, among 27 Image-type datasets, the percentages of times each method achieves the best accuracy levels are 3.70%, 25.93%, 1.85%, 5.56%, 31.48%, 12.96%, 0.00%,

Table 7: Table of Rank Analysis

Method	Device	ECG	Image	Motion	Sensor	Simulated	Spectro	Total Points
C45	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
MLP	0.0	3.0	7.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	5.0	17.0
1NN-Euclid	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.25	0.75
1NN-DTW	1.0	0.0	1.5	2.5	1.75	2.0	0.25	9.0
1NN-LCSS	1.0	1.0	8.5	5.5	2.25	0.0	0.25	18.5
SVML	0.0	1.0	3.5	0.0	2.25	0.0	1.25	8.0
FS	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.75	2.0	0.0	5.75
ARTSC	4.0	1.0	5.0	3.0	7.0	0.0	0.0	20.0
Total	6.0	7.0	27.0	13.0	15.0	5.0	7.0	80.0

and 18.52% for the methods **C45**, **MLP**, **1NN-Euclid**, **1NN-DTW**, **1NN-LCSS**, **SVML**, **FS**, and **ARTSC**, respectively. This table also facilitates interpreting the success of each method by type. For example, **SVML** achieves the highest accuracy for 14.29% of ECG datasets, 12.96% of Image datasets, 15.00% of Sensor datasets, and 17.86% of Spectro datasets, but it does not lead in any Device, Motion, or Simulated datasets. However, **ARTSC** excels with the highest percentages in the Device (66.67%) and Sensor (46.67%) categories, while also performing strongly in Motion datasets (23.08%).

Table 8: Table of Rank Analysis in Percentages

Method	Device (%)	ECG (%)	Image (%)	Motion (%)	Sensor (%)	Simulated (%)	Spectro (%)
C45	0.00	0.00	3.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MLP	0.00	42.86	25.93	7.69	0.00	20.00	71.43
1NN-Euclid	0.00	0.00	1.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.57
1NN-DTW	16.67	0.00	5.56	19.23	11.67	40.00	3.57
1NN-LCSS	16.67	14.29	31.48	42.31	15.00	0.00	3.57
SVML	0.00	14.29	12.96	0.00	15.00	0.00	17.86
FS	0.00	14.29	0.00	7.69	11.67	40.00	0.00
ARTSC	66.67	14.29	18.52	23.08	46.67	0.00	0.00

6. Discussion and Conclusions

This research presents ARTSC, a new time series classification method based on the autoregressive (AR) representation of time series. The algorithm was evaluated on 80 datasets from the widely recognized UCR & UEA time series archive and compared with several popular time series classification methods, including C45, MLP, 1NN-Euclid, 1NN-DTW, SVML, and FS. ARTSC ranked among the top three performing methods in the statistical analysis and achieved the highest overall performance in the rank analysis by dataset type. It also showed strong results on Device and Sensor datasets, suggesting its suitability for these specific categories.

ARTSC’s performance in these dataset categories may be attributed to its ability to address temporal dependencies and nonstationary characteristics in time series data. By dynamically adjusting lag (p) and differencing (d) values, ARTSC transforms nonstationary patterns into a stationary form, facilitating feature extraction. This approach, combined with its feature refinement mechanism, enables ARTSC to effectively handle the dynamic behaviors of Sensor datasets and the temporal complexities of Device datasets.

While the Random Forest (RF) classifier was used in this study as the final step of ARTSC, other classifiers can also be employed. For example, experiments using Support Vector Machines (SVM) at this step showed improved results for approximately half of the datasets. Furthermore, the accuracy of ARTSC could potentially be enhanced by incorporating additional local or global features, such as the mean or standard deviation of the en-

tire time series or its segments. Future research could enhance ARTSC by incorporating advanced parametric time series models, such as GARCH [30], to model time-varying volatility, and ARFIMA [31], to capture long-memory processes, thereby improving its ability to handle complex temporal patterns and enhance classification performance.

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